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THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF SHEIKH AHMAD IBRĀHIM BAMBA TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF HADITH AND ITS TEACHINGS IN NORTHERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The attention devoted by Islamic scholars to the teachings and dissemination of Hadith throughout Islamic history is immeasurable; this is because of its cruciality in understanding the meaning of the Qur'an. Historically, Hausaland has witnessed significant scholarly contributions to Hadith studies since the advent of Islam in the region. Islamic learning continued to expand due to the influx of scholars from different parts of Africa to major centers in Hausaland such as Kano and Katsina. The establishment of Sokoto Caliphate marked a period of rapid growth in Islamic scholarship, during which the progeny of Shaykh Uthman dan Fodio became widely recognized for their substantial contributions to various fields of Islamic knowledge, including Hadith. The greatest book on the study of Hadith sciences known by Shaykh Abdullah Dan Fodio, *Misbāḥ al-Rāwī*, was a great example. Furthermore, their legacies remain intact in Hausaland. In more recent times, Nigerian graduates of the Islamic University of Medinah have further strengthened Hadith scholarship in northern Nigeria. This paper aims to highlight the scholarly contributions of Shaykh Ahmad Ibrahim Bamba, an alumnus of the Islamic University of Medinah, to the study Hadith in northern Nigeria. The contributions of scholars like Shaykh Ahmad Ibrahim Bamba have experience limited researches in academic discourse, and have not been sufficiently studied, this is because of the less attention given to African scholars who have immensely contributed to the interpretation, teaching and preservation of Hadith within their local contexts. The study is therefore, aimed to examine the contributions of Shaykh Ahmad Ibrahim Bamba to the development and teaching of Hadith in Northern Nigeria. The study argues that his contributions extend beyond his uninterrupted weekly Majlis to include the students and personalities he mentored that were became public figures today, and the preserved audio recordings of his teachings, which are accessible and easily understood by Hausa-speaking audiences in the region. Due to the scarcity of documented materials directly related to the subject, this research relies primarily on secondary data, even though the primary has also been used. This study recommends that Ulama should set aside public criticism and embark on teaching and research so that the religious extremism could be deterred, controlled and managed based on knowledge.

Keywords: Hadith Studies; Ahmad Ibrahim Bamba; Islamic Scholarship in Hausaland; Hadith Dissemination; Northern Nigeria

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

The teachings and dissemination of Hadith is an old legacy among the Islamic scholars; this is because of its cruciality in understanding the religion of Allah. The prominence of Hadith scholarship and its dissemination has its ancestry origin among the companions of the Prophet (P.B.U.H). Islam has come to Hausa land which later became northern Nigeria together with its scholarship; the Muslims scholars carry together the call to Islam and the teachings of Islam, thus, Islamic scholarship was massively boosted by more immigrants influx of clerics and scholars from African region to Kano, for instance, Islamic scholar Al-Maghili from north Africa visited Kano and Katsina, the duo therefore, became a second home for many north African Arabs (Abdullahi, 2010).

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Numerous scholars have contributed immensely to the development of Islam and the teachings of Hadith in the region, the notable amongst are: ‘Abdullahi Thiqa al-Fullani, an erudite scholar who was said to be the first person to memorize *Kutub as-Sitta* (the six books containing Hadiths of the Prophet S.A.W) in the region; Alhaj Muḥammad Rāji, one of the Dan Fodio’s Hadith scholars, As-Sheikh Muḥammad Muwaṭṭa, a well-known memorizer of Muwaṭṭa Malik in Katsina (Al-aluri, n.d.). Dan Fodio has also took the scholarship endeavor throughout his life, teaching different fields of Islamic education including *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhāri*, a book which he use to send to his vicegerents emirs when he conquered a state during Sokoto Jihad; his son Muhammad Bello who took over the scholarship activities after the demise of his father, as well as Abdullahi Fodio, the author of *Miṣbah al-Rāwi* (a poem on the science of Hadith).

The legacy left by these great personalities remained intact for several years, the region had also witnessed the scholastic contributions of Shaykh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi, whose teachings rooted the formation of Izala in 1978 (Tsiga, 2016) Gumi gives public preach in Sultan Bello Mosque, Kaduna, teachings *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhāri*, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Muslim* and *Muwaṭṭa Mālik*. (Tsiga, 2016; Shehu, 2022). Not only among the Salafists, there were also prominent figures among the Sufis whose contributions to the study of Hadith in Northern Nigeria are worthy of mention. Notable among them is Shaykh Nasir Kabara (1912-1996), a loyal disciple of Shaykh Ibrahim Natsugune (d. 1941). He studied under him works such as *Muwaṭṭa Mālik*, *Kitāb al-Shifa*, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhāri* and *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Muslim*. Kabara’s Majlis is widely known for its lesson in Hadith literature, especially *Kitāb al-Shifa* by Qāḍī ‘Iyād, a book that contains the biography of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W). He was able to produce over 300 works in various fields of Islamic education, including five works specifically on Hadith. (Muhammad Nasir al-Din, 2010);

Among the contemporary Sufis widely known for their significant contributions to Hadith studies is Shaykh Ibrahim Ṣālih al-Husaynī (b. 1938), who hails from Borno State. His Majlis has been popularly known since the 1980s for conducting lessons in Tafsīr in the Hausa language, as well as Hadith. Through this platform, he has been able to teach *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhāri*, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Muslim* and *Riyāḍ al-Ṣāliḥīn*, in addition to other books on Sufism. He has also authored hundreds of works in various fields of Islamic education. (General Secretariat for Fatwa Authorities Worldwide, n.d.). It is believed that no scholar in the recent time, afar from Gumi, who devoted himself in teaching Hadith like Ahmad Muḥammad Ibrahim Bamba, for he has spent thirty years teaching and imparting the knowledge of Hadith, the impact has beautifully led populace to nicknamed him as ‘Kala Haddathana’. The decade-long contact of Islamic countries such as the kingdom of Saudi Arabia with northern Nigerian citizenry had greatly impacted in the dissemination of Salafism and the teaching of Ḥadīth in northern Nigeria. Graduates of the Islamic university of Medina are prominent leaders in the “Ahlussunnah” network in Kano; (Thurston, 2016), their scholarly contribution in teaching of Hadith and dissemination of Islam cannot be quantified, this is because of the commitment of the university and Saudi national bodies such as: *Dār al-Ifta* in sending delegations of the graduates to disseminate the knowledge they have acquired in the University. This paper aimed at exploring the scholarly contributions of Ahmad Muhammad Ibrahim Bamba (*kāla haddasana*), an alumnus of IUM, to the development of Hadith in northern Nigeria. The study believes that the preserved audio recordings of Bamba could be amongst his greatest contribution of Hadith teachings particularly in northern Nigeria. Furthermore, his contributions were not only restricted to the immediate student he taught but rather, the far away listeners of his audio lectures are also amongst the contributions he made.

Conceptualization of Ḥadīth

Ḥadīth is an Arabic word which its literal meanings include: New (Minshawi, n.d.) (the opposite of old), story, communication or report. (Martin, 2003) Technically, the term encompasses the sayings, actions, affirmation, and attributes of the Prophet (P.B.U.H). (Minshawi, n.d.). The term Sunnah which sometimes used to refer to *ḥadīth* is also conceptualized as the saying and actions of both the Prophet and his companions. Thus, ‘*Ilm al-Ḥadīth*’ is the science of exploring the defect or otherwise in the chain of narration, it is sometimes referring as ‘*Ilm-al-Rijāl*’, *Muṣṭaḥ al-Ḥadīth* or ‘*Ilm al-Isnād*’.

A Brief Overview of Hadith Scholarship in some Northern parts of Nigeria

The history of Islamic scholarship in northern Nigeria could be traced back to the advent of Islam in the region; this is because Islam and scholarship are inseparable. Al’aluri (n.d.) opines that Hausa land, which later became northern Nigeria, has witnessed the influx of various Islamic scholars from North Africa. Kano and Katsina, which were the oldest cities in Hausa land, become centers of Islamic scholarship; the efforts made by Hausa land scholars is paramount in this regard, these scholars include: ‘Abdul Lahi Thiqa al-Fullani, the great scholar who said to be the first to memorize *Kutub al-Sitta* (six Hadith collection) in Hausa land, he sought knowledge in Agadez and Fezzan then returned to Katsina and took up teaching there, he has a poem on the system of preaching and administration ‘*Aṭiyat al-Mu’īr*’; Alhaj Muḥammad Rāji, he was amongst the Hadith scholars of ‘Abdul Lahi Fodio, he performed hajj and met the scholars of the two holy mosques and benefited from them; Ash Sheikh Muḥammad Muwaṭṭa (d. 1850), he had memorized Muwaṭṭa, the famous book of Hadith wrote by Imām Mālik, he learned from Katsina scholars, he taught ‘Abd al-Rahmān As-Suyūfī; Al-Maghili, and ‘Abd al-Rahman Az-Zaiti al-Wankari and other notable scholars visits Kano. Thus, these cities became center of scholarship in the region. (Al’aluri, n.d.).

The region has remained fully established in Islamic knowledge until the era Fodio's progeny, the great revivers of the teachings of Islam in Hausa land, they wrote and taught so many books on different field in Islam including Hadith sciences, the *'Miṣbah al-Rāwī* of 'Abdul Lahi Fodio is a great example, Sheikh 'Uthman also had an *'Aṣr* session in teaching Hadith. (Al'aluri, n.d.) The scholarship impact and legacy left by those notable scholars remained intact up to today, for instance, Abubakar Gumi had spent his life teaching Hadith books such as *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī* and *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Muslim* and other Islamic branches of knowledge. (Tsga, 2016) The attention given to the study of Hadith by Muslims, both in the past and present, stems from its significance and central position in Islam. Likewise, Hausaland has given special recognition to the development of Hadith through teaching, learning, and transmission to both individuals and the general populace. Scholars organized classes for their disciples, often translating the content into the Hausa language. This explains why much of the interpretation of Hadith texts in Hausaland remained unchanged for many years due to verbatim transmission (Musa, n.d.) Categorizes the ways and methods through which Hadith is taught, and highlights some of the popular Hadith books used in these settings:

1. Ḥalaqāt al-'Ilmiyyah (Scholarly Circles)

This refers to gatherings where students sit with a scholar, each with their books, to acquire knowledge. The Hadith books taught in these circles include the six canonical collections (Kutub al-Sittah). Musa further notes that among the pioneering scholars who taught these books were Malam Sabo Zage—who is said to have memorized the Kutub al-Sittah—and Shaykh Ahmad Maḍātai, among others.

Additionally, books such as *Al-Arba'ūn al-Nawawīyyah*, *Al-Muwatta'* of Imam Malik, *Lubāb al-Ḥadīth* authored by Imam al-Suyuti, and *Mukhtār al-Aḥādīth al-Nabawīyyah* were commonly taught and explained in these circles.

2. Majālis (Public Lessons)

These are public gatherings where people come together to listen to Hadith lessons, which are often broadcast on radio stations. Among the books translated into the Hausa language is *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī*, popularized by Shaykh Abubakar Gumi in 1962 through his Saturday and Sunday sessions at Sultan Bello Mosque, which were aired on Radio Nigeria Kaduna; *Kitāb al-Shifā'* by Qāḍī 'Iyāḍ was also widely known through its translation by Shaykh Nāsir Kabara (1924-1996). Similarly, the *Muwatta'* of Imam Malik was taught by Shaykh Dahiru Usman Bauchi (1927-2025) and broadcast on Radio Nigeria Kaduna. Among the scholars who dedicated their lives to teaching and translating Hadith texts is Shaykh Ahmad Ibrahim Bamba, who is the focal point of this paper. It is of great importance to note that the scholars contributed to the development of Islamic scholarship in Hausa land were not necessarily Nigerians, rather, the non-indigenous are also contributing greatly to the development, furthermore, the contact of Nigerian citizenry with other Islamic countries such as Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, had greatly contributed to the development of Hadith in the region.

Life background of Shaykh Ahmad Muḥammad Ibrāhim (Bamba)

Ahmad Muhammad Ibrahim Bamba a Ghanaian citizen, who migrated to Nigeria, was born in Nguwan Gonjawa, a metropolis in Kumasi, Ghana, in the year 1940. His father was Muhammad Ibrahim and his mother was Hajia Khadija (Mma Adizatu), a daughter of Malam Sani, a renowned scholar and the first chief of Gonja community in Kumasi, Ghana. He had 15 brothers with 11 sisters. (Abdulhaq, 2022). According to Sakwaya (2015), Bamba was a former *Tariqa* follower, and was said to be named after Shaykh Amadou Bamba, the Senegalese famous Sufi order and a founder of *Muridiyya* movement (Shitu, 2024).

He had his first and early Islamic basic education at Waṭaniyya Islamic school under its founder, Shiekh Ahmed Baba al-Wa'iz (lived 1913-1982), a Sufi order and spokesperson of *Faīḍah*, however, he proceed to further his education in the field of Islamic Jurisprudence where he studied *Matn al-Ashmāwī* under Malam Amadu Langonto; and later he met and study under a Sunni renowned scholar in Kumasi, Shaykh Abdus Samad Habibullah. Most of the sources consulted by this writer did not provide the elementary schools attended by Bamba, rather, it provides only his interest in Islamic education, and that there were some Egyptian instructions sponsored by their government who came to Kumasi and establish a school called Markaz Al-Sharif, which Shaykh Ahmad Bamba and his colleague Mallam Muntari enrolled themselves and after various pattern of studies, the instructors noticed Shaykh Ahmad Bamba was a repository of retentive memory, it was on that experience he was offered an opportunity to advance his knowledge in Egypt before his depart to Medina, KSA, to study under the collage of Hadith sciences where he obtains his B.A, in the sciences of Hadith at the Islamic university of Medina, (Abdulhaq, 2022) and according to one of his students (Indabawa, 2024), he also bags his M.A and PhD at Bayero University Kano; however, this claim requires further documentary verification as the exact date of graduation remains unrevealed.

Life in Medina and Kano

Bamba was said to be amongst the most talent students in the Medinan University, as he was able to be amongst the great disciples of the renowned scholar of the Faculty of Hadith in Islamic University of Medina, Sheikh Ḥamad Al-Anṣārī (lived from 1925-1997), and a respected scholar attracting students worldwide to seek accreditation from him, in fact, he worked for him about eight years as research assistant in Medina (Darulfikr, 2021).

Bamba left behind a great record during his tenure as a student, and was recommended as a great Muḥadith (expert in Ḥadith) by the Islamic university of Medina, this led the management to send him for the task of propagating Hadith in India, but due to language barriers, he could not fulfill the task, (Indabawa, 2024) he later on sent by *Dār al-ʿIftā*, through the request of the then H.O.D of the department of Islamic studies, to teach Tafsir and Ḥadith teachings at Bayero University, Kano (Dankwano, 2024). He started public service as a lecturer at Bayero University, Kano in 1981, even though several graduates of Medina and Sudan’s International University of Africa teach at the Aminu Kano Collage of Islamic and Legal Studies holding positions as deans and heads of the departments. (Thurston, 2016), built a wide audience through his teachings of *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī* in Saturdays and Sundays at Ummah Mosque old campus B.U.K, in 1991. (Shehu, 2022) During his stay at Kano, Bamba, had experienced several challenges both from the staff of the university and the town inhabitants, this had led him to resigned from his position and migrate to Niger republic in 1996-1997. (Dankwano, 2024; Daneji, 2024)

Bamba was known for his endurance in teaching. He held his Hadith Majlis for over thirty years without interruption, during which he taught the major hadith collections, including the six books of al-Sunan. This was confirmed by him in lesson 7 of Kitāb al-Zuhd from Sunan Ibn Mājah, where he stated that his uninterrupted majlis began on 2nd November 1992 and continued until September 2016. This was about six years before his death in 2022, during lesson 100 of Sharḥ al-Sunnah. His position in knowledge led people to engage him in refuting the heretical ideas of fabricators; he once dialogues Sudanese scholar, Bashir, who resides in Kano before his migration to where he named *Dār al-Salām* at Mokwa local government in Niger state; Bamba refutes his radical doctrine of *Takfīr*. (Adda’wah, 2022)

In his book, *Salafism in Nigeria*, Thurston, (2016) argues that Medina graduates are obtaining financial support from various sources such as: Al-Muntada al-Islam Trust, which led the establishment of mosques and schools in Kano, such as Al-Furqan Mosque. However, this is not the case in the initial life-time of Bamba’s struggles, as he went various tragedies including being a taxicab driver between Kabuga and Gwarzo highway. (Redman, 2022).

The Contributions of Sheikh Aḥmad Bamba to the Development of Ḥadith in Northern Nigeria

While assessing the contributions of Shaykh Ahmad Bamba on the development of Hadith, the following points should be taken into cognizance, these include:

- His weekly Majlis at old campus, Bayero University Kano then his center, Darul-Hadith, Tudun-Yola, Kano. The center was reported to have established formal primary and secondary schools. (Daneji, 2026)
 - The students he taught and mentored.
 - The books he wrote or transcribed by his students.
1. The weekly Majlis of Bamba has started in 1991; (Shehu, 2022) he was able to begin with the most authentic book after holy Qur’an, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī*, this book has been thought by different scholars in their Majlis. For example: during the time of Shaykh ‘Uthman Dan Fodio, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī* was the amongst the books he is sending to his Amirs in the conquered towns, urging the Amir to teach his people Tafsir of Jalalāin, *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī* and Risala of Abi Zaid; Shaykh Abubakar Gumi also teaches *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī* in his Majlis in Sultan Bello Mosque, Kaduna. When Gumi noticed that people need to know purification first, he steps down from teaching Hadith and begins teachings books on jurisprudence, such as *Matn al-Akḥḍari*, *Matn-al-‘Ashmāwiy* and *Muqaddimah al-Izziyā*.

Bamba’s style of teaching Bukḥari differs with some of the Muḥaddithūn (scholars of Ḥadith), he focuses only in the interpretation of the context of the Hadith without explaining the defect or otherwise in the link of the narration (Isnād).

Bamba’s best contribution to the development of Hadith is his uninterrupted weekly Majlis in the great books of Hadith which include:

- a. *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukḥārī*; he started teaching the book at old campus of Bayero university, Kano in 1991; in seven-hundred and fifty-four (766) lessons.
- b. *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Muslim*; Started 6 July, 2022.
- c. *Sunan Abi Dāwūd*
- d. *Sunan at-Tirmidhī*
- e. *Sunan Nasā’ī*
- f. *Sunan Ibn Mājah* ended on June 2018
- g. *Muwaṭṭa Mālik* started 8 October, 2016, ended 9 October, 2018 in one-hundred and sixty-two (162) lessons.

- h. *Sharḥ al-Sunnah*; started 31st October 2020 and stopped at one-hundred lessons on 3rd January 2022

During his teachings of the aforementioned books, Bamba attracts large number of audiences in northern Nigeria, particularly in Kano where his center Dārul Ḥadīth located; recorded audios of his lecture are accessible in websites by far away audience.¹

2. Bamba had numerous students whom he mentored, those students were regarded as his contributions to the development of Hadith, because most of his great students today have impacted and transmitted the knowledge they acquired from him to their immediate community. Today, they are holding great positions in the universities and are either Islamic leaders or Imams, the notable students of Bamba include:
- a. Sheikh Ja'far Maḥmūd Ādam (1960-2007): a popular and renowned scholar of Tafsīr in northern Nigeria.
 - b. Mu'azzam Khālid Suleiman PhD: a graduate of Islamic University, Medina.
 - c. Abdul-Qādir Ismā'īl Kabara PhD.
 - d. Professor Ṣaliḥu Lawal Malumfashi; a Hadith scholar in Katsina state.
 - e. Idriss 'Abdul-'aziz PhD; a popular scholar in Dutsen-Tanshi, Bauchi state (Musulunci, 2023)
 - f. Shaykh Sani Yahaya Jingir; a famous scholar and the leader of *Jamāatu Izālatul Bid'ah Wa Iqāmat Sunnah*, national headquarter Jos, Plateau state (Bichi, 2022).
 - g. Sheikh Aminu Ibrahim Daurawa; a renowned scholar and the acting commander in-chief of Hisba commission, Kano state (Shehu, 2022).
 - h. Abdullah 'Uthman PhD; a renowned scholar and Imam at 'Uthman Ibn 'Affān center, Gadon-Kaya, Kano.
 - i. Shaykh Lawal Abubakar Shu'aib, popularly known as Lawal Triumph. (Daneji, 2024)
 - j. Umar Ibrahim Indabawa PhD; a senior lecturer at the department of Islamic studies, Bayero University, Kano. He took over the teaching activities at Darul-Hadith center, Tudun-Yola, after the demise of Bamba in January, 2022.
 - k. Professor Ahmad Murtala, former head of department of Islamic studies, Bayero University, Kano.
 - l. Kāsīm Ramadan PhD, senior lecturer at department of Islamic studies, Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano. (Dankwano, 2024)

These famous scholars were not only the students of Bamba; rather, his students were as many as possible. As stated previously, he taught for almost thirty years in the university, therefore, as a specialist in Hadith, he taught Hadith as a course in the class and the students in other field use to attend his class of Hadith, in the process, the beneficiaries became his student (Shehu, 2022).

3. Writing and publishing is a daily basis of an academic so also a scholar, for it is through writings and publication knowledge and information are preserved. Bamba, as an academic and famous scholar, has his own publications and writing which are termed as his contribution to knowledge, despite the fact that he did not write much in the field of Hadith, and most of his writings remained unpublished, this researcher has able to discover some of his published writings in the field of Hadith, below are amongst:
- c. His work on *Juz' al-Qirā'a Khalf al-Imām*, a book authored by Imam al-Bukhārī; Bamba edited (Taḥqīq) the book and filtered the accepted *ahādīth* in the book in 1978. (Darulfikr, 2021). Below is the picture and some fragment content of the book:

جزء البقرة، ذ خلف الإمام

للإمام أبي عبد الله محمد بن إسماعيل البخاري أمير المؤمنين
في الحديث رَحِمَهُ اللهُ تَعَالَى
١٩٤ - ٢٥٦ هـ

تحقيق وتخرىج وتعليق
أحمد محمد إبراهيم

أستاذ العقيدة والتفسير والحديث وعلومها
بقسم الدراسات الإسلامية جامعة عبدالله بايرو بكنو حرسها الله
نيجيريا

وبذيله رسالة الإمام الشوكاني، رحمه الله
في أن مدرك الركوع مدرك للركعة

ورسالة: قوة الحجاج في عموم المنفرة للحجاج
بمخاتمة الحقاظ، أتحافظ أحمد بن حنبل
العقلا في رحمه الله

طبع

بعناية لجنة تصحيح العقيدة والسلوك
التابعة لجماعة الدعوة في نيجيريا
ص.ب ٦١١٨ كانو - نيجيريا

دار العربية

Figure 1:
Cover page

الفهرس

٥ المقدمة
٩ مقدمة المحقق
١١ ملنقط من القصيدة النونية
١٣ جزء القراءة خلف الامام
١٥ باب: وجوب قراءة الفاتحة في الصلاة
 باب: وجوب القراءة للإمام والمأموم وأدنى ما يجزي
٢٣ من القراءة
٤٥ باب: هل يقرأ بأكثر من فاتحة الكتاب خلف الإمام
٧٩ باب: لا يجهر خلف الإمام بالقراءة
٨١ باب: من نازع الإمام القراءة فيما جهر لم يؤمر بالإعادة
 باب: من قرأ في سكتات الإمام إذا كبر وإذا أراد
 أن يركع
٨٣ باب: القراءة في الظهر في الأربع كلها
٨٥ جواب الإمام محمد بن علي الشوكاني في ان مدرك الركوع مدرك
 الركوع مدرك للركعة
٨٩ قوة الحجاج في عموم المغفرة للحجاج
٩٧ فصل: في ضبط الأسماء والألفاظ الواقعة في هذه الطرق على الترتيب
١١٧ الفهرس
١٢٠

Figure 2:
Reference

- a. He was able to edit 'Umdat al-'ulamā' authored by Shaykh Uthman dan Fodio in 1984, the original manuscript is accessible in the internet however, the edited copy was not found by this author. (Darulfikr, 2021)
- b. An Audio transcribed book of *Muwatta Mālik*; this book is a collection recording of his lectures in *Muwatta Malik*, which was transcribed and written in Hausa language.

A far from the abovementioned books, there were unpublished books written by Bamba in other field of Islamic knowledge, and it is not out of content to mention them here even though the books were not in the Hadith but his works on those books could be ascribed to his contributions on Hadith development, as he commented on the books of Dan Fodio and his son Muḥammad Bello, the books include:

1. *Al-Buzūr al-Mushfirah Fī Kiṣāl al-Latī Yudrak bihā al-Maghfira* of Muḥammad Bello (Unpublished)
2. *Attambihāt al-Wādhāt Fīma Jā Fī al-Bāqiyāt Aṣ-Ṣālihāt*-Bello (Unpublished)
3. 'Umdat al-'Ulamā' of Dan Fodio (Unpublished)
4. *Kalimat at-Taḡwā* authored by him and published. (Idris, 2024)

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Over the years, Northern Nigeria witnessed a great influx of Islamic scholars from different parts of Africa. This is why the advent of Islam in Nigeria was closely tied to Islamic education, as the region witnessed the visitation of great scholars such as al-Maghīlī, al-Suyūfī, and others from different fields. These scholars left a significant legacy, which contributed to the region becoming a center of Islamic literature. The outcome of this legacy led to the emergence of scholars in various fields, including Hadith studies.

One of the greatest factors that facilitated the growth of scholarship in Hausaland was the existence of active Da'wah movement in the region. Sokoto, Kano and Katsina witnessed influential drivers of change in Islamic knowledge. Among the earliest introducers of the Kutub al-Sitta in Hausaland were Sufi scholars, such as Abdullahi Thiqa, Nasiru Kabara, among others, who were committed to the teaching and commentary of Hadith texts, as stated in Kabara's works. The graduate of the Islamic University of Medinah, in recent years, has also contributed immensely to the development of hadith literature in Northern Nigeria. Scholars such as Shaykh Aminuddin Abubakar 1947-2015. Shaykh Abdul-Wahhab Abdullah (b.1953) , and Shaykh Ahmad Bamba have greatly contributed to this development. However, many scholars' contributions remain unknown and under-documented due to a lack of academic documentation and recognition.

This paper examines Shaykh Ahmad Bamba's consistent public Hadith recitation as his contribution to the development of Hadith studies in Northern Nigeria. The paper does not, in any way, neglect the efforts of other Hadith scholars whose written works remain their greatest legacy in Hadith studies, among whom are Shaykh Ibrahim Salih al-Husayni, Shaykh Muhammad Sani Umar, and others.

Recommendation

For academic researchers: Special attention should be given to uncovering and studying the efforts and contributions of Hadith scholars within local contexts, particularly those who have dedicated their lives to teaching and serving humanity. For the government and philanthropists: They should assist and support individual scholars by providing national awards and recognition for their significant contributions to preaching and promoting national unity. For students: Greater attention should be given to selecting research topics that highlight and uncover the contributions and efforts of such scholars. For the general populace: Qualified experts in Hadith should be entrusted with the teaching and interpretation of religious texts, including Hadith, due to their crucial role in understanding Islam.

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